

EFFECT OF PRESSURISED HYDROGEN ON LOW CYCLE FATIGUE OF INCONEL 718: MODELLING AND TESTING

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Inconel 718 is used for many technical applications. However, it is known that it is prone to hydrogen embrittlement. The tubular specimen technique is used for strain controlled low cycle fatigue (LCF) tests at 0.1 Hz with internal pressurised hydrogen at 10 bar and 100 bar. The comparison to reference tests in air shows the effect of the different hydrogen pressures on the fatigue lifetime. For a better understanding of a possible influence of the tubular specimen geometry, reference tests on conventional specimens were completed. The results are used to propose a model based on a damaging parameter to have a better prediction of the fatigue life.

The experiments on tubular specimens with internal hydrogen gas pressure showed a significant reduction of ductility in the tensile tests and of fatigue life in the LCF experiments compared to tests in air. A Manson-Coffin strain-life curve was fitted to the data obtained in air and modified to conclude from the ductility loss in the tensile test under hydrogen to the fatigue life under hydrogen. Thereby, a good agreement with the experiments could be achieved.

Keywords: Low cycle fatigue, Hydrogen embrittlement, Tubular specimen, Life prediction

INTRODUCTION

The goal of a climate-neutral economy is rapidly increasing the need for carbon-neutral hydrogen applications. In order to realise and improve these technical applications, high-strength materials are required. Inconel 718 is widely used in the fields of aerospace, oil and gas industry and nuclear reactors due to its high strength and good corrosion resistance (Konečná et al. [1], Puydebois et al. [2], Galliano et al. [3] and Kolts et al. [4]). However, it is known that Inconel 718, as well as other high-strength metallic materials, can be subject to severe embrittlement and reduced service life of components when in direct contact with gaseous hydrogen. It is therefore particularly important to carry out experiments under the relevant operating conditions and to be able to predict service life of the components.

Carrying out the experiments under different hydrogen gas pressures and temperatures can be very complex and expensive, especially when it comes to fatigue experiments with long test times. The experiments are usually carried out in expensive autoclave test systems with high safety precautions due to the risk of hydrogen explosion. The tubular specimen technique offers a cheaper alternative, with less safety precautions and can be implemented on existing testing machines. Therefore, an axial hole with a small diameter is drilled through a specimen and filled with pressurised hydrogen

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gas (Michler et al. [5], Michler et al. [6], Ebling et al. [7], Ogata [8] and Ogata [9]). This means that the volume of hydrogen in the specimen is small and the specimen can easily be heated or cooled from the outside. This leads to a significant reduction in the effort and thus also the costs of experiments.

Furthermore, the testing effort can be reduced by models. These models should be validated on a small number of tests and thus be able to make statements about a large field of operating conditions.

MATERIALS

In this work, additive manufactured Inconel 718 was used. It is a precipitation hardened, nickel-based superalloy. The heat treatment was conducted according to SAE AMS 5663 [10] with solution annealing at 980 °C for 1 hour and a two-step aging at 720 °C and 620 °C for 8 hours, respectively. The microstructure of the transverse and longitudinal additive material is shown in the micrographs in FIGURE 1. The specimens were manufactured from blanks. For the tubular specimens, a 2 mm hole was drilled through the longitudinal axis of the blanks first. Then the contour was worked out centred on this hole. The outer surface of both, conventional and tubular specimens, was polished along the gauge length. The geometries of the conventional and tubular specimens can be seen in FIGURE 2.

Tensile and low cycle fatigue (LCF) experiments were conducted on a Walter + Bai LFMZ 100 kN universal testing machine. To measure displacement in tensile and fatigue experiments, two different clip-on gauges with measuring lengths of 31.25 mm and 10 mm, respectively, were used. Tensile tests were conducted in displacement control and a speed of 0.001 mm/s. LCF experiments were carried out strain controlled with a negative strain ratio of -1 and a frequency of 0.1 Hz. Three different strain amplitudes were tested, which were 0.55 %, 1 % and 1.5 %. For experiments with hydrogen, tubular specimens were flushed 10 times and filled with hydrogen gas of $\geq 99.9999\%$ purity.

FIGURE 1 Light microscope micrograph of additive manufactured Inconel 718 transversal (left) and longitudinal (right) to building direction.

FIGURE 2 Conventional low cycle fatigue specimen (left), tubular low cycle fatigue specimen (center) and tubular tensile test specimen (right).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The tensile tests conducted in air and filled with 10 bar and 100 bar pressurised hydrogen gas can be seen in FIGURE 3. While yield strength and tensile strength are not significantly affected by hydrogen, the elongation to failure ϵ_f is slightly reduced when tested with 10 bar hydrogen pressure and strongly reduced with 100 bar hydrogen pressure. The experiments in air and with 10 bar hydrogen were each repeated once. These showed only a small scatter in both strength and elongation to failure. Therefore, these were not shown in the diagram for better clarity.

FIGURE 3 Tensile tests on tubular specimens in air and filled with 10 bar and 100 bar hydrogen gas.

The relative elongation to failure can be used as a comparative value for the ductility of a material between air and hydrogen tests. It is defined by

$$R\epsilon_f = \frac{\epsilon_{f,H2}}{\epsilon_{f,Air}} \tag{1}$$

where ε_{f,H_2} is the elongation to failure with hydrogen gas and $\varepsilon_{f,Air}$ is the elongation to failure in air. Another characteristic value for the ductility is the relative reduction of are RRA which is defined by

$$RRA = \frac{RA_{H_2}}{RA_{Air}} \quad (2)$$

where RA_{H_2} is the reduction of area with hydrogen gas and RA_{Air} is the reduction of area tested in air. The results of the tensile tests are listed in TABLE 1. For the following model, the value of the relative elongation to failure is used as a measure of ductility under hydrogen.

TABLE 1 Mechanical properties of additive manufactured Inconel 718 on tubular specimens in air and filled with 10 bar and 100 bar hydrogen gas.

	$R_{p0.2}$ (MPa)	R_m (MPa)	ε_f (-)	$R\varepsilon_f$ (-)	RA (%)	RRA (-)
Air	1036	1284	0.175		22.2	
10 bar	1044	1290	0.157	0.897	18.0	0.807
100 bar	1012	1244	0.08	0.457	14.7	0.663
Repeated tests						
Air	1041	1288	0.178		19.8	
10 bar	1062	1300	0.162		18.8	

The low cycle fatigue experiments on conventional and tubular specimens tested in air can be seen in FIGURE 4. Both, conventional and tubular specimens show about the same number of cycles to failure N_f for all three amplitudes. To fit a Coffin-Manson model, the strain amplitude ε_A is plotted versus $2N_f$ in a log-log diagram. Equation (3) can then be used to describe the strain-life relation as a function of the elastic and plastic strain amplitude

$$\frac{\Delta\varepsilon}{2} = \varepsilon_A = \varepsilon_{A,el} + \varepsilon_{A,pl} = \frac{\sigma'_f}{E} (2N_f)^b + \varepsilon'_f (2N_f)^c \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_{A,el}$ and $\varepsilon_{A,pl}$ are the elastic and plastic part of the strain amplitude, respectively, σ'_f the fatigue strength coefficient, ε'_f the fatigue ductility coefficient, N_f the cycles to failure and E the elastic modulus. The exponents b and c are the strength and ductility exponents, respectively, Socie et al. [11]. By fitting the elastic and plastic strain amplitude, the values in TABLE 2 are obtained.

FIGURE 4 Low cycle fatigue experiments on conventional and tubular specimens tested in air with Coffin-Manson fit on experiments with tubular specimens.

TABLE 2 Material coefficients for Coffin-Manson model.

	E (MPa)	σ'_f (MPa)	b	ϵ'_f	c
Air	183613.5	1580.9	-0.05345	2.10734	-0.76842

Manson proposed the four-point correlation method and the method of universal slopes in 1965 to estimate fatigue life from tensile tests. He was able to make a good estimate for 29 materials from different material classes and was thus able to show that the material properties from tensile tests can be correlated to the fatigue life, Manson [12]. Therefore, in the following the loss of ductility ϵ_f in the tensile test under hydrogen pressure is used to correlate the fatigue ductility ϵ'_f and estimate the fatigue life under hydrogen pressure. For this, the material coefficients gained from the experiments in air and the fatigue ductility coefficient, multiplied by the relative elongation to failure $R\epsilon_f$, are used for the Coffin-Manson model under hydrogen pressure. This results in the pressure-dependent fatigue ductility coefficient $\epsilon'_{f,H_2}(P_{H_2})$ for the hydrogen experiments.

$$\epsilon'_{f,H_2}(P_{H_2}) = R\epsilon_f(P_{H_2}) * \epsilon'_{f,air} \tag{4}$$

The values that result from this for the two different hydrogen pressures are shown in TABLE 3.

TABLE 3 Fatigue ductility coefficients adapted for hydrogen gas pressures.

Hydrogen pressure P_{H_2} (bar)	ϵ'_{f,H_2}
10	1.89028
100	0.96305

Using the coefficients from TABLE 2 and the fatigue ductility coefficients from

TABLE 3 results in the representation of FIGURE 5. The 4 fatigue experiments at 10 bar and the 6 experiments at 100 bar internal hydrogen pressure with different strain amplitudes are well on the adjusted lifetime curves. Due to the low scatter in the experiments, good agreement with the modelled curves can already be seen. Further experiments should be carried out to statistically confirm the result.

FIGURE 5 Low cycle fatigue (LCF) experiments on tubular specimens in air and filled with 10 bar and 100 bar hydrogen gas. Coffin-Manson fit for air and for hydrogen with adopted fatigue ductility coefficient ϵ'_{f,H_2} .

SUMMARY AND DISCUSSION

First, tensile tests were performed on additive manufactured Inconel 718 with tubular specimens filled with internal hydrogen pressure. The relative values $R\epsilon_f$ and RRA were calculated for a comparison between hydrogen and air tests. Here, it was shown that at the high pressure of 100 bar

$R\epsilon_f$ reacted more sensitively to hydrogen than RRA . Michler et al. conducted comparative tests between conventional and tubular specimens on austenitic steels and could see that the relative reduction of area of tubular specimens showed less sensitivity to hydrogen than the conventional specimens did. The value $R\epsilon_f$ was not evaluated in this work and the difference in RRA between conventional and tubular specimens could not be explained by finite element modelling [5].

Low cycle fatigue tests comparing conventional and tubular specimens were performed. Here, no significant difference in the lifetime between the two specimens types could be found. This is in contradiction with Gill et al. [13] where a finite element analysis was conducted to study the geometry influence of tubular specimens. They found that multi-axial strain occurs and leads to reduced cycles to failure. Roughness and residual stresses in the bore may have an influence here and should be investigated further.

The LCF tests showed a strong hydrogen effect on the fatigue life of additively manufactured Inconel 718, and this effect was strongly dependent on the hydrogen pressure. A Coffin-Manson model was fitted for a strain-life curve. In order to represent the hydrogen effect and to be able to estimate the fatigue life under hydrogen gas pressure from simpler and less expensive tensile tests, the hydrogen pressure-dependent fatigue ductility coefficient $\epsilon'_{f,H_2}(P_{H_2}) = R\epsilon_f(P_{H_2}) * \epsilon'_{f,Air}$ was introduced for the Coffin-Manson model. A good agreement with the LCF experiments with internal hydrogen pressure could be achieved. Thus, the ductility loss obtained from tensile tests can be used to predict the reduced fatigue life under hydrogen gas pressure.

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